
UNDERSTANDING HINDU MARRIAGE: CONTRACT OR SACRAMENT

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ABSTRACT

The Hindu Marriage Act was introduced on May 18, 1955. It applies to all Hindus, Jains, Buddhists, and Sikhs and also applies to other persons who are not Muslims, Parsis, Jews, and Christians unless they establish that Hindu customs do not govern them. Hindu marriage has long been a source of controversy; some scholars see it as a contract, while others see it as a sacrament. This essay examines Hindu scriptures, legal legislation, and the essence of Hindu marriage. Hindu marriage is necessary for the survival of the family and society. Additionally, this paper argues that Hindu marriage includes both sacramental and contractual components.

I. INTRODUCTION

In India, marriages are considered a vital part of everyone's life. Hindu marriage customs and rituals must be strictly adhered to for the union to be fulfilled. Matrimony is the establishment of a relationship between a husband and wife. It's been claimed that a marriage is an unbreakable tie that lasts beyond death. Hindu marriage dates back to the Vedic era and is a longstanding custom.

India is the only nation that practices Hinduism, which has its own culture, traditions, customs, and rights. There are 16 Samskaras in total, with marriage, or Vivah, being the most significant since it involves seven steps and vows made in front of Saptapadi, the fire. In Hinduism, it is a fact that man is incomplete without his wife. In our community, the grihastha referred to as a married life, is extremely important. Shastras also said that a man cannot effectively carry out all of his responsibilities in the absence of a woman, or vice versa. Therefore, marriage is essential to become whole.

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II. HINDU MARRIAGE AS A SACRAMENT

Hinduism views marriage as a sacrament, a holy and religious responsibility that is necessary for the continuation of the family and society. It also holds that each Hindu has a specific life mission, which is represented by the purusharthas, which are dharma, Artha, Kama, and Moksha. Hindu marriage ceremonies include customs and traditions such as the saptapadi, which is seven steps around a sacred fire to symbolize the union's sanctity.

The wife is also called Ardhangini which is known as half of man and man is not complete until he marries. The sacramental nature of marriage has three characteristics: -

- It is a permanent union
- It is an eternal union
- It is a holy union

Section 7 of The Hindu Marriage Act provides:

Ceremonies for Hindu marriage

1. A Hindu Marriage may be solemnized in accordance with the customary rites and ceremonies of either party thereto.
2. Whether such rites and ceremonies include Saptapadi (that is, the taking of seven steps by the bridegroom and the bride jointly before the sacred fire), the marriage becomes complete and binding when the seventh step is taken [1].

In the case of Shivonandh v. Bhagavathymma, the court observed that marriage was binding for life because a marriage performed by the saptapadi before the consecrated fire was a religious tie that could never be united.

In the case of Tikait v. Basant, the court held that marriage under Hindu law was a sacrament, a dissoluble union of flesh with flesh and bone with a bone to continue even in the next world.

III. HINDU MARRIAGE AS A CONTRACT

The modern concept of marriage as a contract sprang from the lofty ideals of liberty and equality of the industrial revolution. The greatest contribution of the Industrial Revolution was the emergence of the concept that all human and social relations should be based on the freedom of individuals.

Section 5 of The Hindu Marriage Act provides: -

Clause(ii) and (iii) of The Hindu Marriage Act contain the pertinent provisions to determine Hindu Marriage Act as a contract.

Conditions for Hindu marriage

1. A marriage may be solemnized between any two Hindus, if the following conditions are fulfilled, namely:
2. At the time of the marriage, neither party
 - (a) is incapable of giving a valid consent to it in consequence of unsoundness of mind;or
 - (b) though capable of giving a valid consent, has been suffering from mental disorder of such a kind or to such an extent as to be unfit for marriage and the procreation of children;or
 - (c) has been subject to recurrent attacks of insanity.
3. The bridegroom has completed the age of [twenty-one years] and the bride, the age of [eighteen years] at the time of the marriage.

The Hindu Marriage Act's Section 5(ii) states that both parties must give valid consent and be of sound mind. Clause (iii) on the parties' ages expressly states that the groom and bride must be at least 21 and 18 years old, respectively, and that these requirements also apply to contracts.

Looking back at Hindu history, Manu states that Kanyadana, or the gift of a lady, is a fundamental aspect of Hindu marriage that has been practiced since the Vedic era. It is performed by the woman's father by entrusting her hand and her household responsibilities to her husband. It

becomes a contract since it can be seen as a gift. But rather than getting consideration from both sides, there is only one of them.

Furthermore, Section 13 of the Hindu Marriage Act, which addresses divorce, disproves the notion that marriage is an everlasting and permanent relationship that cannot be ended at any cost. Both parties may end their marriage on several grounds. They can get married again after a divorce. The Widow Remarriage Act breaks the idea of an eternal union by allowing widows to remarry.

The Hindu Marriage Act's Section 8 introduces the concept of marriage registration, which is essentially a type of contract. In Hindu marriages, the idea of registration did not exist previously. Nonetheless, registration is optional right now. State governments have the authority to require it if they so choose. The state may even impose fines for failure to register. In the case of *Purshotamdas v. Puroshotamdas* [3], it was decided that the parents' consent on behalf of the parties is considered legitimate in Hindu marriages.

Hindu marriage is ruled to be both a sacrament and a contract in the case of *Bhagwati Saran Singh v. Parmeshwari Nandar Singh* [4]. In the case of *Dhanjit Vadra v. Beena Vadra* [6] it was held that Section 13-B radically altered the legal basis of Hindu marriage by treating it as an ordinary form of contract which competent parties can enter into and put an end to like any other contract by mutual consent. In the case of *Seema v/s Ashwini Kumar*⁷, the Hon'ble Supreme Court held that registration should be made compulsory by the state government.

IV. CONCLUSION

We have looked into the perspective of both marriage as a sacrament and marriage as a contract. Vedas and Shastras also view marriage as a sacramental union, and there are rituals associated with sacramental character that are necessary for marriage. However, as society advanced, the idea of a contract changed, and other elements were added to marriage as well. The Hindu Marriage Act has provisions that imply marriage is a contract as well.

However, those are not precisely the same. There are several variations that we have observed in contracts related to marriage. Hindu marriage can be viewed as a combination of sacrament and

contract because it incorporates the viewpoints of both parties, rather than being a pure contract or sacrament.

References

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